

An Urban Utopia for an Ethnic Minority: Calcutta in Baghdadi Jewish Fiction

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The city has been the site of desire since the rise of ancient urban civilizations. The desire to control, dominate, and contour the population as well as the urban landscape has been a primary drive of civilisations. Plato's ideal commonwealth is a rationally ordered and hierarchically organized city-state, and Lewis Mumford traces the rise of the Ancient Egyptian and Mesopotamian archetypal city as a sacred site, symbolic of a heaven on Earth, or in other words, a *Utopia* (Mumford 1965, 272). The city has always been in the domain of the unreal, differentiated from the landscape surrounding it; it is both an idyllic space and a site of unfulfilled desire. Thomas More defined the term much later in his seminal *Utopia* (1516) as possessing this dual meaning—*eu-topos* (a happy place) and *ou-topos* (no place), emphasizing the impractical nature of such perfection. Thus, a utopian space contains within itself the dichotomy of being both desirable and un-achievable. In a utopia,

Equality, social justice, and the elimination of social hierarchies are often central tenets. Cooperation and communal living, where individuals work together for the collective good, are frequently emphasized. Harmonious

coexistence with nature, sustainable practices, and environmental stewardship are valued in many utopian visions. Education and intellectual development play a crucial role, as utopian societies prioritize the pursuit of knowledge, personal growth, and lifelong learning. (Singh 2022, 944)

From More's imaginary island society with its ideal socio-political structure to contemporary utopias of practice such as Auroville (a spiritual, sustainable, township in India which emphasizes on a communal eco-friendly lifestyle), and the kibbutzim (collective communities based on shared labor and ownership in Israel), a utopia has always been a model for a better life.

Yet, it is also characterized by hostility, as most utopian states are totalitarian, with absolute disregard for minorities. From Aristotle to More, no utopian thinkers could conceive of an ideal space devoid of race, class, and gender hierarchies. "Isolation, stratification, fixation, regimentation, standardization, militarization" are the parameters that demarcate a utopian city (More 1965, 277). The reason for this authoritarian impulse is that the origins of utopia lie in religion- utopia is a sacred space, created according to the desire of the ruling class, who have always claimed to be agents of God. Thus, patriarchy and oppression are rooted in a utopian city and indeed drive it, and eventually, utopia emerges as dystopia for its minority population, which threatens the city with their *otherness*. Further, the ruling class controls the narratives that emphasize the need for boundaries and hierarchies separating them from the *other*. In colonial Calcutta, the British would publish essays and narratives that portrayed the *white* town (the European quarters) as a utopian space separated from the filth and chaos of the *native* black town. In contemporary Israel, the state uses media to underscore the importance of Jewish urban centers of development in Tel Aviv, and contrast them with poor, underdeveloped, dystopian spaces inhabited by the Arab communities in Rahat and Gaza.

Thus, the question then is not how an ideal space is achieved, but rather, would this utopian state be advantageous to every individual living within it? The other equally important question is, what constitutes a utopian space for a minority community living in an adopted land? This paper attempts to answer both of these questions with regard to the Baghdadi Jewish community of Calcutta. The first section will be an in-depth look into what utopia means in Judaism, and how it has been realized through the Zionist movement and the creation of Israel, as well as highlight the involvement of the Baghdadi Jews in this ideal Jewish commonwealth. The second section will be an analysis of postcolonial Calcutta as a utopian space for the Jewish community as seen through the prism of Jael Silliman's novel *The Teak Almirah* (2016).

The Baghdadi Jewish community is one of the three prominent Jewish groups in India along with the Bene Israelis and the Cochin Jews. Their moniker is a symbol of their Middle Eastern origin, and although they were termed Baghdadi Jews since most were settled in Baghdad, they had also migrated to India from Basra, Aleppo, and other regions. During the 19th and 20th centuries, they adopted the colonial cities of Calcutta and Bombay as their residence and aligned themselves with the British in order to attain a superior position in the complex socio-political structure of colonial India. The writer and academic Jael Silliman is a prominent member of this community. Silliman identifies herself as an Indian and qualifies her Jewishness as an identity but not a lived reality. (Silliman 2001, 135) She has contributed immensely to her community through her written narratives, her digital archive *Recalling Jewish Calcutta*, her interviews, and lectures on the Jews of India, particularly that of her community. Additionally, she is a feminist scholar who is actively promoting women's reproductive rights and third world women's movements. Much like her other narratives, *The Teak Almirah* (2016) is concerned with the relationship between Jewish characters and the city of Calcutta. It portrays the city through the perceptions and expectations of its protagonists, and as such reflects on its simultaneous

utopian and dystopian overtones. To understand a utopian reading of Silliman's text, it is imperative to understand the importance of utopia for global Jewry.

I

The idea of the formation of an ideal motherland, which all Jews could claim as their own without any discrimination, had been present in Jewish collective consciousness since time immemorial. One could trace such desires to the moment of their expulsion from ancient Palestine (Canaan) under Roman, Byzantine, and Islamic empires. Jewish migrants scattered around the world and formed diasporas in Europe, Africa, and Asia, each rooted in their religious and ethnic identity. As Jews living in Europe became accustomed to ideas of Enlightenment and state centralization, the need to assimilate within the mainstream European societies became central to their identity. However, the more they were integrated in European nations, the more they were persecuted and discriminated against by the mainstream population. The rising anti-Semitism led many thinkers to challenge notions of integration and instead propose radical measures such as Jewish socialism and ethnic nationalism. Zionism emerged in the 19th century as one such radical idea that advocated a Utopia for all Jews regardless of their nationality, race, or class. The birth of Zionism is due to the confluence of two contradictory movements- the Enlightenment of West Europe with its emphasis on individuality, and the state centralization and absolutism of East Europe with its drive towards ethnic collective identity. It arose due to the "disenchantment (of European Jews) with liberalism in Western Europe, combined with political upheaval and violence in Eastern Europe, a setting more generally conducive to thinking about identity in ethno-nationalist terms." (Halperin 2016)

The idea that Judaism and Jewish subjectivity can only be realized in an independent state consisting of Jewish administrators and clergy originated in Leo Pinsker's seminal text, *Autoemancipation* (1882).

However, it was the Viennese-Jewish journalist Theodore Herzl who turned out to be the strongest proponent of the Zionist movement, which he claimed was an answer to anti-Semitism. (Gorny 1998, 242) Indeed, the initial Zionist trend focused on Judaism's idea of the creation of a utopian land which would be located on the topos of the ancient Jewish motherland which was situated in the Arab populated Palestine. This space would at once assert their independence from Europe and reinforce the connection to their ancestors. For every generation of Jews had their own image of this utopia which they passed on to the next generation through fables, songs, and other mediums of popular culture.

Thus Israel, for the Zionists, was the utopia which had underpinnings in religion as well as politics. As European Jews started migrating to Israel, the focus shifted from integration to separation of Jews and local Palestinians. The first wave of Jewish settlers established plantations by occupying Arab lands which were then maintained by cheap, hired labour from the local Arab population. From the beginning, the European Jews distinguished themselves as enlightened, educated, and superior to the Muslim population. As the second wave of immigrants arrived, they were displeased to see their predecessors being so reliant on the Arabs. They believed that Jewish identity should be integral to the soil they live in, and hence socialist ideas of labor and ethnic nationalism rooted in the Hebrew language were promoted, which further alienated the Palestinians who had now lost both land and labor. A growing anti-European sentiment was spreading like wildfire in the Arab world and Palestine was not immune to this. Jews who settled in Palestine realized it but refused to heed the local Muslims. Due to the harrowing after-effects of the Second World War and the Holocaust, large numbers of Ashkenazi (European) Jews were forced to emigrate to Palestine and the international pressure on the newly formed United Nations led them to declare the Partition Plan for Palestine in 1947 which came into effect after the British mandate expired in 1948, and thus Israel was born. Gregory Claeys remarks that "Dystopia...rather

than being the negation of utopia, paradoxically may be its essence. Any privileging of the communal over the individual will for some have dystopian overtones.” (Claeys 2018, 15)

The intention of the Jews was to establish an ethno-national state built according to the blueprint of east European nations, one that would not harbor any difference within its population. Much like More’s Utopia, Israel is an authoritarian regime where individuality is superseded by the collective and ethnic minorities face immense discrimination. The sense of distrust and despondence gradually was building up between the settlers’ and the local Arabs, further escalated by subsequent fundamentalist regimes. Thus, the dream of the Jews became the nightmare of the Arabs. However, it was not just the latter who were coerced into submission- the Jews themselves were racially segregated as well.

From the very beginning Zionism divided diasporic Jews in two broad categories: *Ashkenazi* (Euro-American white Jews) and *Shephardim* (later named *Mizrahim*) who are *Jews of colour*. The question of utopia always revolved around the former, and the latter were not taken into account by the proponents of Zionism. It is ironic that a movement emerging as a protest against racial prejudice in Europe would inherit the same prejudices. But radical thinkers were determined to separate cosmopolitan Western Jewish identity from the Eastern inferior one. In the process, they eliminated any difference existing within the European Jews themselves and created the image of a monolithic European Jewish identity originating from Western capitalist cities. Once again, this is in accordance to the totalitarian utopian state, which emphasizes binaries. In the binary of Ashkenazi/Mizrahim, the latter got suppressed and erased from the Jewish legacy. The Mizrahim immigrants, a population which includes the Baghdadi Jews, were treated very differently to their European counterparts. They were forced to settle in poor, rural areas, and often provided manual labor for the Ashkenazi. In a crueler episode, several Yemeni Jewish children were kidnapped and donated to

childless Ashkenazi couples. (Massad 1996, 56) Much like the “white man’s burden”, the European gentile Jews believed that their purpose was to educate and “raise the Eastern Jews to their culture without being ‘brought down’ to their “primitive levels.” (Massad 1996, 57)

When Baghdadi Jews of India migrated to Israel, they were settled in transit camps unlike the European Jews, who were given houses to reside in. They survived in dystopian conditions where there were scarcities of water, food, and other resources. They managed to do so on the strength of their belief in a better life in the Holy Land. Although to the early Baghdadis, Israel was a utopia due to its religious history, the later generations developed a sense of community and Israeli secular pride. They actively westernized themselves in order to fit within the spaces of the Ashkenazi-Israeli utopian state. The price of this was paid by the erasure of Baghdadi Jewish identity among descendants as well as the absence of Baghdadi Jewish history from mainstream Israeli narratives. Thus, the utopian state of Ashkenazi Jews was hostile and estranged from the Baghdadi Jewish population. Often mistaken for their Arab Muslim brethren, the Baghdadi Jews faced xenophobia and racial discrimination in communal spaces and had to prove their identity to the authorities. Although due to their eventual assimilation within Israeli society, their social position has improved, there still lingers certain prejudices which put them in a subservient position compared to their European counterparts.

II

Calcutta has always been a city of contradictions, and as such has elicited a wide spectrum of responses from its local as well as its visiting population. Since its beginning, the city was divided into two halves- the utopian white town denoting the affluent areas where Europeans resided and the dystopian *black* town characterized by filth and poverty, located in fringe regions and inhabited by the locals. From its conception as an urban center connecting the various trade ports of Asia to its flourishing as the colonial capital, the city had been marked

by a modernity quite unlike the other historic cities of India. One marker of this colonial modernity was the project to have it mapped and controlled. It is therefore unsurprising that the initial phase of the reception of Calcutta was grand and spectacular- a utopia which projected the wealth and strength of the British Raj in the East. British writers particularly were keen on this impression and very soon Calcutta, and more precisely the white town attained the title “City of Palaces”. It was an unreal space where magic and reality mingled to resemble the (Greek mythological) idyllic “garden of Hesperides”, according to Atkinson. (Banerjee 2019, 55) This perception of the city was reflected in Mughal writers as well, as Mirza Ghalib famously calls it a “heavenly city, free from all cares.” (Banerjee 2019, 57)

As the nineteenth century progressed, this image of a utopian city was replaced by one where filth and squalor were the defining characteristics. British writers gradually started portraying a dismal picture of a city that had improper infrastructure, lacked hygiene, and desperately required maintenance. Unsurprisingly, instead of holding the British governance responsible, they piled the blame on the locals of Black town, whom they began to categorize as barbaric and lacking discipline. Indeed, one of the primary reasons for Calcutta’s portrayal as a dystopia in colonial British literature was the fear that the Black town was impenetrable and hence one could not set up surveillance; this led to the ever looming risk of another revolt like the one of 1857. In the Mughal tradition, the image of the city was gradually becoming dystopian as well, but for another reason- as Mirza Ghalib deftly claimed in his later poems, it is a beautiful city without a soul, where the only importance lies in commerce and nothing else. (Banerjee 2019, 58)

This coldness of the city is depicted in the Bengali tradition of writing Calcutta too; Bhabanicharan Bandyopadhyay commented that the city lacked any form of moral or religious core. The wealth as well as the diversity created a lax attitude amongst its Bengali population, and an apathy towards people from rural Bengal. (Banerjee 2019, 59) Each of these traditions regarding the perception of Calcutta left an imprint on

its future residents even after the city had undergone enormous changes post-independence.

The fictional narrative of Jael Silliman that I shall be analyzing in this paper will reflect some of these trends. It must be remembered that while narrating a city in fiction the author uses both her real experiences of living in the city, as well as the conceived space of the imagined city, thus producing layers of urban formation. In Silliman's narrative, post-independence Calcutta in its entirety is neither a utopian nor a dystopian space, rather it is remarkably neutral, and caters to its inhabitant's outlook and imagination. However, there are particular enclaves in the city which provide the promise of utopia, and other spaces which highlight the dark, distorted, reality hiding underneath the surface of the city. For this paper, I shall employ the epithet *Calcutta* to signify both the colonial and the postcolonial metropolis, instead of the parochial *Kolkata* for it is the former (an elite, cosmopolitan, urban space) which the Jewish community identifies as their adopted homeland.

In *The Teak Admirah* (2016) Silliman unveils fragments of the lives of four Baghdadi Jewish protagonists, entangled in a web of faith and nostalgia, each viewing Calcutta through the prism of their own pre-conceptions and prejudices. As a result, the city forms myriads of images in the narrative, which can be broadly categorized into *the city that is* and *the city that should be*. The city then becomes at once real and imagined, each co-existing with the image of the other. The space of the narrative, therefore, is disjointed, fragmented, contradictory, and revelatory as we follow the characters trying to straddle between their expectations and their realities.

To Tamara Silas, Calcutta is *a city of desire*, a space far away from cold, clinical, London, where she can re-invent herself as a dancer, and as a Jew. The city is symbolic of her paternal roots, of her father's Jewishness, which her mother had refused to acknowledge or discuss with her after his early death. The emotional connection she has with her father is reflected within the space of the city, and Calcutta becomes

synonymous with her father, and evokes his essence in its warmth and conviviality. From the moment she lands in Calcutta, she finds it familiar as if they had an old bond, and yet it exceeds her expectations. More than anything, the city holds the promise to make her *whole* again. As she understands from Hanif Kureishi's *The Buddha of Suburbia* (1990), "it is important to embrace both sides of oneself." (Silliman 2016, 12) Calcutta sharply contrasts the barren, half-truths of London, where her English mother had desperately prevented her from discovering her Jewish roots. The city is exultant and expressive, and it reflects Tamara's ecstasy in wish-fulfillment.

Ernst Bloch observes that daydreams along with fairy-tales, are important utopian elements, which are "escape attempts" for people to change their position in the world, in order to envision a better future. (Bloch 1986, 195) All her life, Tamara had fantasized about travelling to the extravagant world of the *Calcutta* in her father's bed-time stories. After his death, her longing for him intensifies her desire to visit this utopian land. Her warmest moments in her childhood were when she would listen to Samuel's own childhood adventures and visualized the hot summers, and dense forests of India. In many ways therefore, her visit is actually a return to the safe-space of her childhood. However, Tamara also understands the incongruous reality of the city--- old, dilapidated mansions flanked by brand new shopping malls and apartment complexes. She gets particularly jarred while passing through Rajarhat, pointing out the *ghost* buildings made of metal and concrete which seem like a different world compared to Ballygunge where she resides,

Rajarhat is indeed a dystopia- it suggests the unity of the most virtual form of capital accumulation and the primitive form. Eviction, threat, coercion, murder, gun running, and the presence of bands of coolies from Murshidabad and Malda — these combine with shiny glass buildings, e-firms. (Dey 2016, 17)

The juxtaposition of the old and the new is reflected in the disparity between the appearance and morality of the locals as well. Tamara feels instantly attracted to Rita, the dance teacher from the city, with whom she is to work. It is Rita who volunteers to be her travel guide and together they journey across the city, unravelling its many mysteries and myths. As they walk through the lanes of Ballygunge, Tamara gets dazzled by the vibrant colors of the city which are heightened in the summer heat. Calcutta seems unreal to her, as if part of a waking dream. She learns more of Rita's Bengali middle class background, and shares stories of her English upbringing. As their friendship deepens, their desire for each other intensifies. Yet, when Tamara invites Rita to explore beyond the boundaries of heteronormativity, she denies her advances awkwardly. Tamara realizes that underneath the surface of a progressive woman, Rita adheres to an Indian middle-class morality that views homosexual relationships as a social taboo. But her companionship with Rita yields more than sexual desire, it reveals spaces of utopia in the city- it is Rita who makes Tamara's voyage of self-discovery a seamless experience. Leslie Kern remarks that,

The power of female friendship is typically either underestimated, undermined, or ignored altogether in cultural narratives... For far more ordinary women, friendships are also part of our urban survival toolkits... Friendships with other women also shape the ways that women engage with the city itself. (Kern 2021, 59-60)

Female friendships create a strong support system for the woman to navigate in an urban space which is otherwise quite hostile to her. Not only does Rita become the buffer between Tamara and the harsher realities of a foreigner in Calcutta whose naiveté could be taken advantage of, she also makes Tamara realize her sexual desire once again. Tamara had been heartbroken after her failed relationship with Edith, and had been aloof and lonely, but the city and Rita provoke her with their sensuousness.

If Tamara's expedition is marked by friendship, desire, and wish-fulfillment, as its utopian impulses; Mordy Ezekiel, another Baghdadi Jewish traveller to the city, has an entirely different experience. Mordy had left his parents in Calcutta at twenty-one, to settle in Australia for better opportunities, and had never fulfilled his promise to return to the city while they were alive. Although he had spent his formative years in the city, the latter had no significant influence over him. Indeed, Calcutta for Mordy is a distant memory, a quiet backdrop to his childhood days, and it is only after his return that he realizes how estranged he is from the city. Dystopia is marked by a remarkable anxiety, which causes uneasiness and even paranoia in the visitor. Dystopian spaces display "ways of life we must be sure to avoid"(qtd. in Claeys 2010, 107) – in the unlikely event that we can agree on particulars. Sanghita Sen observes that a dystopian space has four fundamental characteristics- it is "disharmonious, dehumanizing, inhospitable, and devoid of hope." (Sen 2019, 5)

Mordy finds Calcutta to be hot, filthy, and unbearable. He gets incredibly cantankerous over the pollution, traffic, and lack of order in the roads of the city when he visits his parents' graves at Narkeldanga. Indeed, chaos is one of the chief features of a dystopian space. Lack of order, political corruption, and ill-maintained infrastructure are the first things Mordy notices about the city. He keeps asking the question "how do people breathe here?" and compares the lackadaisical rules of the pedestrian pathways to the pleasant sidewalks of Australia. The myriads of sounds of the city which appealed to Tamara is a cacophony and an insult to Mordy's senses. Dystopia is also marked by an absence of memory and a disjoint in historical continuum. However hard Mordy tries, he cannot remember details of his old life in the city. He asks himself how he could have survived in this hot and dusty space as a child and contrasts it with his seemingly perfect life near the beautiful Bondi Beach. Yet, his life in Australia was far from a utopian existence- between financial constraints in his early career, and an ill wife, despair had always followed Mordy. He could not fulfil the one promise he had

made to his parents, and loneliness had been a constant companion, particularly after his wife's death. It was the material pleasures and a well-maintained city that had constructed a utopian bubble for Mordy in Australia, regardless of its trials. In contemporary Calcutta however, there is no such security and Mordy realizes just how vulnerable and lonely he is as an old man in a space that would not cater to him. He desperately longs for the old utopian order--- the colonial city where his ancestors flourished, and he finds it in certain spaces in the city.

The first such location is the Narkeldanga Jewish cemetery, which although ill-maintained and derelict, retains a connection to his roots. As he surveys the gravestones and reads the words engraved on his parents' headstones, he is moved by an enormous burden of guilt and nostalgia, and a sense of primitive grief and solace overcomes him. It is this utopian space that spiritually connects him to his ancestors and to the larger Baghdadi Jewish community. Through the act of reading the barely legible names on the gravestones while picking up small pebbles from the soil, he vows to remember them (*a promise*), and it is only then that old forgotten memories start reappearing to him. While returning from the cemetery, even as he is rattled by the honking cars and the incessant traffic, Mordy cherishes the warm, colourful memories of his childhood.

Gregory Claeys notes that, in a dystopian space human volition is superseded and eroded by an external authoritative force. (Claeys 2015, 17) This is remarkably true for Seemah Elias, one of the last remaining Jews of Calcutta. Seemah was once the inhabitant of a city which was the destination for cabaret artists, and jazz singers. Park Street was a sensation where brass bands would perform for a cosmopolitan audience, and entertainers from all over the globe would captivate an elite, liberal audience, educated in western values. Although the city she inhabits now is independent, and has its own identity, free from western shackles; she regrets that corrupt political parties and trade unions have led to many businesses close shop and leave. The new businesses and

establishments are struggling as well under bureaucratic pressure, and as her friend Annie points out, everyone in the city is trying to cheat each other. (Silliman 2016, 7). Utter mismanagement has led to hawkers flooding the streets, and Park Street now sees the familiar view of pedestrians bargaining for cheap goods from street vendors. Although Seemah's utopian Calcutta too had immense irregularities and discriminations, her privileged position in the old order naturally makes her unconscious of those drawbacks.

Instead, Seemah tries to maintain order within the little sphere she occupies- through a perfectly tidy and formulated appearance and through her relationships with her maid and her driver, both of whom have served her family for ages. She had carefully preserved the ancient furniture and paraphernalia in her home, and had even worked at the little press that her family has been running for decades. Indeed, Seemah is a woman of discipline, and she refuses to change her lifestyle to accommodate the transforming city. She has witnessed urban utopian operations turning the city into a dystopian nightmare, particularly in two instances. The first being the Naxalite movement of the 1970s which started as a class struggle to overthrow the elite, but which subsequently descended into deadly clashes between the police (along with the Congress government), and the radical supporters of the movement, particularly the students (Manhas 2021, 74). The other was the state government launched *Operation Sunshine* of the 1990s, which strived to remove hawkers from the streets and which eventually transformed into an unsympathetic, brutal exercise of the government on the working class.

Seemah embodies the spirit of an old world and through her spatial practices, she sustains her utopian dream. And therefore she never quite fits in with the real city. This is reflected through the space in which she resides- her airy, spacious ancestral flat with its high ceilings and large verandah with a lawn in which orange-red Gulmohurs blossom, is a stark contrast to the high-rising apartment complexes all around it. The

private space of her home gives her refuge to the disorder and flux of the city, and it is here that she can be herself and dream of a better future. Therefore the space of her home becomes a *heterotopia* which accumulates history, and memory to preserve dreams and hopes. Michel Foucault envisions heterotopia as relational to utopia. Just like the latter, heterotopian spaces too have an inverted spatial order, separated from the larger urban space. The difference between the two is that while utopian spaces are imaginative- usually envisioned and dreamed of, heterotopian spaces are actively practiced. James Faubion defines Heterotopias as “realized utopias” (Dehaene and Cauter 2008, 31). They are “sites of marginality that act as postmodern spaces for resistance and transgression.” (Hetherington 2006, 41). Foucault muses that,

There are also, and this probably in all culture, in all civilization, real places, effective places, places that are written into the institution of society itself, and that are a sort of counter-emplacements, a sort of effectively realized utopias in which the real emplacements, all the other real emplacements that can be found within culture, are simultaneously represented, contested and inverted; a kind of places that are outside all places, even though they are actually localizable. Since these places are absolutely other than all the emplacements that they reflect, and of which they speak, I shall call them, by way of contrast to utopias, heterotopias. (Dehaene and Cauter 2008, 17)

Thus, Seemah’s house becomes a site of resistance to the urban modernity of the post-independent city. It becomes a *heterochrony* (a space where multiple periods of time co-exist) by freezing time and memories, both fundamental to utopias. Seemah is immensely protective of this other space. Her verandah overlooks a stretch of land which hungry land sharks had converted from an extended lawn to a multi-storied apartment. Seemah calls this space a *dobhi-ghat* due to the clothes hanging from its many balconies. Raucous music and garbage bags mark

the site and the residents often throw garbage even into her garden. The day she finds condoms and sanitary-pads in her lawn, she threatens them that she would throw them right back. Seemah feels increasingly lonely and violated by the chaos of the loudspeakers and the filth in her surroundings. Therefore, she becomes more fiercely attached and defensive of her oasis although sometimes she does feel that such order leads to a lackluster life. It is then not surprising that, her home is the haven where the other protagonists seek solace and develop a sense of family among each other.

Thus, both the dystopian spaces as well as the utopian ones are relational to and co- exist with the intermediate *real* space of the city. It must be noted that utopian sites can be characterized by anxiety too, for the inhabitants of the space are constantly conscious of the precariousness of their positions. Such is the fate of Firoza, a Parsi woman living in Mumbai who has constructed and conditioned her existence on her faith. She has lived her life under the shadow of her fierce, protective mother Sunoo Ardeshir, who taught her Parsi values and had never failed to stand up for her. After a failed marriage to a Parsi man, Firoza finds herself distraught and desperate, and it is her mother who is a constant companion to guide her. Therefore when Sunoo dies, Firoza's harmonic, stable world seems to be on the verge of collapse. In a tragic turn of events, Firoza discovers that she was adopted by Sunoo, and that her whole life had been an elaborate façade; she collapses under the burden of the enormous falsities. The truth haunts her as the *uncanny*, and she realizes that it was her dear uncle Parvez who had an affair with a Jewish woman, Seemah, and both, understanding their ethno-religious differences, gave Firoza to Sunoo, with Parvez agreeing that he would never reveal the truth. While Firoza eventually comes to terms with her crisis in faith, Seemah has always lived with the guilt of her actions. She had voluntarily avoided marriage and had led a liminal existence while nightmares had consumed her at night. Thus, for Seemah dystopia and utopia co-exist in the same space, creating a volatile order. Her home is both her refuge and a reminder of her actions, which is reflected in the empty teak almirah, symbolic of

the hollowness of the space she resides in. Indeed, Foucault remarks that heterotopias represent several sites incompatible with one another. The purposes of heterotopia changes to suit the requirement of the moment- therefore the site which provides her privacy also becomes the site to echo her guilt.

While hopes and dreams are very personal acts, they have a communal origin. The dreams of an individual are dependent on the myths and stories that have been accumulated in her subconscious. Therefore, ethnic communities usually have similar characteristics for an ideal state. To the Baghdadi Jews of the narrative, a utopian state means communal presence and harmony of the members, being recognized and remembered by mainstream Bengali society, and being able to practice their religion, food, and festivities without any intervention. The synagogue is one such communal utopia, where the community members met each other, performed their religious rites, gossiped about the latest news, and celebrated the High Holidays. One particular feature of this shared Utopia is *Verabredung* (literally meaning: meeting) or the secret protocol, which the members of the space share with each other through oral narratives and myths. Historical traces retained in collective memory are transmitted through personal oral narratives from generation to generation. This creates shared memory, companionship, nostalgia, and passing of tradition from older to younger generations, all within this coveted utopian space inaccessible to outsiders.

In the novel, the meeting of the characters produce this utopian hope. The Fairlawn Hotel is one such space where Mordy finds both refuge and companionship. Although old and rundown, this hotel is a reservoir of memories for the community since it was once the home of an elite Jewish woman, a Mrs Curlender whom Mordy remembers. Just like Seema's home, this hotel retains an otherworldly feel to it. For the rest of the guests, it is an emblem of the colonial city with its ancient wooden structures, but it codifies the historical continuum of the Baghdadi Jews to its members. It is here that Mordy befriends Tamara, and they share each other's stories of Calcutta. Mordy begins to realize

that perhaps he was too quick to dismiss the city, and in Tamara's presence he becomes more hopeful for his future. Each provides what the other had always desired- Mordy becoming a father-like figure to her, and Tamara quite naturally assuming the role of the daughter Mordy had always wanted.

When both of them meet Seemah at her home, it becomes yet another space of attachment. Seemah educates them on the achievements of the Calcutta Jews. She invites them in her private utopia and brings them closer to their culture through food, history, and religious practices. With Seemah's knowledge, and Tamara's enthusiasm, Mordy feels enlivened and reflects on his purpose in Calcutta. It is their shared actions that create a communal utopia and constructs a pseudo-family. For like Mordy, Seemah too finds a daughter in Tamara. She teaches Tamara how to perform the rites of the Sabbath, and abandons her routine to accommodate the latter's whims. Ashcroft determines that utopia represents "the spirit of hope itself, the essence of desire for a better world." (Ashcroft 2012, 2) It is through each other's company, that both women fulfil the gaping void in their lives and find a home in each other. Ultimately, it is the interpersonal-relationships which determine a utopian space.

Seemah invites Tamara to fill the almirah with her belongings, and together they celebrate their new dreams with Mordy. Later, when Firoza is finally ready to forgive Seemah and re-invent herself, she visits Seemah's home and each woman share stories of their lives with the other. Oral narratives are an important aspect in constructing a harmonious space. As Seemah tells Firoza the truth that she had hidden all her life, she feels a lightness within her. The heavy silence that wreaked havoc on her conscience finally erupts, and in that moment, Firoza sees herself in Seemah, a woman struggling to live up to the expectations of her community. She realizes that Seemah too was conned as she had been promised by Parvez that she could be in contact with her child. Firoza re-discovers herself in the hybrid space of her

Parsi-Jewish identity through her art, which now portrays a fragment of Calcutta and her Baghdadi-Jewish heritage. This is much like Tamara, who also had re-invented herself as a fusion dancer of Flamenco-Kathak to celebrate her Anglo-Judaic heritage.

Thus, the paper inspects the two-fold questions of what constitutes utopia for diasporic minorities, and what is the position of minorities in a utopian state. In doing so, it throws the spotlight on the co-existence of utopian and dystopian spaces. Indeed, while the state of Israel as a Zionist utopia exhibits authoritarian tendencies and marginalises its minority communities thereby containing within it seeds of dystopia; for Jews of Calcutta, the city contains both utopian and dystopian enclaves often in close proximity to each other. It is in the act of finding one's home (both literal and symbolic) and community, that one enters a utopian space. Silliman's narrative reflects upon the function of utopia as a coveted place, where hope, memory, and history intersect and create a harmonious existence for the inhabitant. For an ethnic minority, the act of story-telling serves an important function in producing a utopian space. Silliman comments that through remembrance, re-telling, and performance of socio-cultural practices, individuals in an ethnic community can maintain this utopia and re-invent themselves. *The Teak Almirah* therefore functions as a text which preserves through its intersecting narratives and evocative story-telling, the memories of Jewish spaces in a city that is forgetting about its Judaic history.

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